

ISSN - 2321-2551

Peer Reviewed & Referred International Journal

CHALUKYA JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

**Indexed with International
ISSN Directory, Paris**

VOLUME : 1 • ISSUE : 1 • DEC 2013

**Founder Editor : Dr. S.G. Dollegouder
Editor : Dr. H.B. Jalajakshi**

CONTENTS

No		Page No.
1.	Environmental Awareness At Different Levels - Dr. Sama Nayak	1
2.	Dr. B.R. Ambedkar's Concept of Social Justice and its Contemporary Relavance - Dr. B. Babu Rao	9
3.	The Study of Socio-Economic Condition of Dalit-Plantation Workers at Nadavali Grama Panchayat - Dr. Govindaraju. B.M.	14
✓ 4.	Education Among Muslims : Sachar Committee Perspective and Suggestive Prospective Strategies - Ms. Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari., Dr. Mushtag Ahmed I.Patel	20
5.	Higher Education, Policies and Muslim Youth - Talat Fatima, Dr.Shashikala D.J.	27
6.	Women In Administration - Dr. H.B. Jalajakshi	35
7.	Idol Sculpture of Muddebihal Region - Prof Basavaraj S.Math	41
8.	Problems in Accessing UGC Infonet E-Journals consortium among the research Scholars : A Survey of Karnataka University Library - Dr. R.R. Naik., Mr. Anand Ra	47
9.	Congress (I) Party's Approach to Liberalization and Globalization And Foreign Policy of India : An Analysis - Dr. Krishna Hombal	58
10.	Rural Sustainability : Women and Local Self Governance - Dr. Meenakshi Bharatanoor	66
11.	Online Database Content Usage pattern in academic community : A Study Based on the Survey of Selected University Libraries of Karnataka - Dr.R.R. Naik, Santosh Chavan	73
12.	Principal : A Fulcrum of Higher education - Dr.S. G. Dollegoudar Patil	82
13.	Right to education Act 2009 : Problems and Perspectives - Dr. k. Rajani Kumari	86
14.	Teaching and Learning Practices in India - Trends and Challenges - Dr. S Usha Sri	93
13.	Role of NGOs in women Health Progress - Divyanetra, Dr. Shashikal D.J.	102
14.	Muslim Child Labours in Bidar District : A Sociological Study - Shekhappa Gyanappa, Dr.Shashikala. D.J.	109

EDUCATION AMONG MUSLIMS : SACHAR COMMITTEE PERSPECTIVE AND SUGGESTIVE PROSPECTIVE STRATEGIES

Ms. Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari,
Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel.

Introduction

India is a vast country with huge population and it is a home for every sixth person in the world as its population constitutes 16% of the world population. Interestingly, every 6th person in India is a Muslim by faith, as they are 16% of India's population. The progress of all individuals is important for the progress of a nation. To give an analogy, if the vehicle of the nation is to be moved forward to the category of developed nation, then all the wheels of the vehicle are to be tidy. The 6-wheeled vehicle can not move ahead smoothly with huge load of information, technology, social, cultural, education ethos, values or the loads to the secured destination with a punctured wheel. Hence, progress and development of Muslims in India is as important as the progress of Indian population in general. But, the nation India is as such still a developing nation. This means that there is problem somewhere in Indian society. On close examination, one of the problem appears to be with Indian Muslim society's backwardness. This hypothetical view is given visibility by the findings of Sachar Committee. This is the main achievement of the committee as once the disease (problem) is diagnosed (researched), then the doctor (government) can take up remedial measures (plans, policies, programmes).

Among the factors which are critical for human development are the human resource potential, which is determined by the educational progress. It is noteworthy that the Sachar Committee devotes a complete chapter on the education of minorities. The authors try to highlight important aspects discussed in this chapter and side by side these are being critically examined so that further researches can be taken up.

Constitution of Committee

The Prime Minister of India appointed a high level committee to look into the social, economic and educational status of Muslim community in India under the chairmanship of Justice Rajender Sachar. This committee consisted of seven members including 4 Muslim members. It is observed that in the list of the members the government could have involved representative of Muslim religious groups (Mullah's) and women. However, the committee

Ms. Mohasina Anjum A. Ansari, Research Assistant, CSSEIP, MANUU, Gachibowli, Hyderabad

Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel, Associate Professor in Education, DDE, MANUU, Hyderabad

later on met representatives from such groups in course of its discussion. But, members from such sections could have given good contributions and inputs in writing of report.

Methodology adopted

The data was generated from the 2001 census and other departmental surveys, sample survey etc. The committee held discussions with volunteers, organisation at various places. Newspapers and other means of communication were utilised for contacting communicating volunteers, and inviting for discussions. Presuming that the entire society's dynamic data is made available through these means in a document is improper. Many more documents and research works are to be referred before generalisation. Few critics also criticise the authenticity of the census process and data itself. Sitting at a particular place and gathering data is also being criticised by many. Because, ground realities may be still worse than what was discussed by the volunteers. A proper mechanism has to be developed for study of various aspects of minority community like, social, education, economic conditions. Scholars from Universities must be encouraged to take up initiative regarding this. The Sachar committee report presents a bird's eye view but at the same time it is a snap shot of what the community is today. But, the future aspects and previous impediments have to be strictly studied. This will help in planning strategies to overcome difficulties.

Some critics who are main opponents to the political parties in power have argued that if the discussions are held with any stakeholder communities, then they will provide list of problems being faced by them. This they argue may be true with any community, caste, whether forward or backward. Hence, they have strong criticism towards the methodology adopted by the committee.

Few observations of the committee and discussion are given below. Here discussion about important aspects of the report (italic) and observations are written simultaneously.

•“The State shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age six to fourteen years...” (Art. 21 A of constitution).

87 The government has ensured free education to all the sections of the society. The education provided is not necessarily be in mother tongue Urdu of children. This has lead to a mismatch in the minds of the children. Thereby, compulsory education has become a theoretical aspect and the Muslim children are practically going away from education. The constitutional provisions are lost due to this scenario. Hence, the right to education act (2009) to be unsuccessful.

•The availability of Census data on educational attainments by religion for the first time since Independence has enabled the Committee to examine the temporal trends in educational attainments.

The data obtained from the census were utilised for preparation of the report, but this presents only a snapshot picture of the society. The status, changes in the dynamics

of society from time to time, region to region and situation to situation cannot be seen. Hence, continuous study is required.

- Many so-called literates did not have the ability to apply their reading and writing skills to real-life situations, and often a substantial proportion reverted to illiteracy within 4-5 years of leaving schools.

The observation of literacy among learners is not sufficient. Practical measures have to be suggested for giving permanent literacy among learner.

on of educational opportunities. The constitution does not discriminate the citizens of India based on caste, creed and/or religion. But, this is not enough for the backward community like Muslims. They are to be given special provisions like SCs, STs for educational upliftment.

- Primary education seems to be the major hurdle for school education.

All the educationists believe that primary education has to be given in mother tongue of the child. Here, the education in non-mother tongue like regional languages or English languages make the child feel alienated and hampers learning. To overcome this hurdle in school education, it is suggested that the Sachar committee or its follow-up action committees must have suggested for provision of ample number of Urdu primary schools, which is the mother tongue of large number of Muslim children across the nation.

- Drop-out Rates among Muslims are highest at the level of Primary, Middle and Higher Secondary compared to all the SRCs.

The managers, administrators schools need to work for bridging the gap between the school and community. This is the only way through which the drop-out rates can be reduced.

- The setting up of Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalayas in rural areas was expected to reduce the supply side constraints on good quality education ... Muslim participation in these schools too is not satisfactory.

There is an urgent need to setup schools, which are primarily targeted for education of Muslim. These schools should be residential in nature and quality teachers must be recruited for teaching from same community. All the teaching facilities have to be provided.

- Since artisanship is a dominant activity among Muslims technical training should be provided to even those who may not have completed schooling.

This is a welcome move. This helps in increasing employability skills and thereby socio-economic status of children can be raised. This in turn may be useful for educational status of future generations.

- The disparity in Graduation Attainment Rates is widening since 1970's between Muslims and all other categories in both urban and rural areas.

Observations and suggestions

Following section critically examines various important facts mentioned in the Sachar Committee report.

- The government has ensured free education to all the sections of the society in its constitution. The report quotes,

“The State shall provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age six to fourteen years...” (Art. 21 A).

The education provided here does not necessarily means education in mother tongue of children i.e. Urdu medium. This has lead to mismatch in the minds of the children. Thereby, the compulsory education has become a theoretical aspect and the children are found practically going away from education. The constitutional provision loses its importance, if this is seen in the context of only one article without studying other provisions.

- The data obtained from the census and other sources were utilised for preparation of the report, but this presents only a snapshot picture of the society in a particular time period. The still picture of society is inappropriate as if and changes in the dynamic society from time to time, region to region and situation to situation. Hence, data from different perspectives have to be analysed to give a comprehensive picture.

- The observation of literacy rate among learners is not sufficient. Because, literary skill fades as time passes without being practice. Practical measures have to be suggested for giving permanent literacy among learner.

- The low literacy rate cited in the report is an impact of lower facilities available for Muslim community. The low literacy effect is compounded effect of past experiences of individuals and the society. Hence, the low literacy has to be seen in global perspective with large comprehensive view.

- The socio-economic status makes the members of the community to commence work at a younger age both in urban and rural areas. The women folk are bound by purdah system and are protected lot. It is also observed that there is hesitation of a section of this society to explore nature and natural process like medicine and birth control etc. This cultural background of the community is not protected in general schools. This has reduced their participation in educational endeavours.

- Muslim leaders and community have to strive for community's upliftment. The government has to open institutes for the benefit of Muslims in their locality and medium. The Muslims have to form societies and associations, which have to be given due weightage in expansion of educational facilities.

- The parents' education, income, social settings, number of family members, school facilities, unfamiliar content in the textbooks etc. may be the cause of dropout of the children and this has to be studied by the research scholars of education.

- There is increase in percentage of enrolled students among Muslims, but at the same time the non-enrolled students give a larger number than previous years due to increased population. Moreover mere enrolment in school is not complete education, the government has to ensure retention of these children, equitable and quality education to all learners including Muslim children. In absence of such a mechanism this helps schools to show teacher pupil ratio and thereby it is a tool to save jobs of teachers.

- The government has to focus such enrolled and never attending students, identify their problems and take initiative for bringing them back to school. The problems may be multifaceted viz., language, school facilities, curriculum content, teaching facilities etc. Hence, a thorough research is required to be done on all these aspects.

- The low levels of attainments of Muslims indicate that the governmental interventions of Operation Black Board (OBB), District Primary Education Programme (DPEP), Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) are going in vain. The main features like enrolment, retention, equity and attainment are not fulfilled.

- The government has made longitudinal and horizontal expansion of educational opportunities. The constitution does not discriminate the citizens of India based on caste, creed and/or religion. But, this is not enough for the backward community like Muslims. They are to be given special provisions like Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs) for their educational upliftment. The educational opportunities are to be expanded in multiple dimensions. This includes separate schools, teachers belonging to their communities, reduction in fees etc.

- All the educationists believe that primary education has to be given in mother tongue of the child. Education in non-mother tongue languages at primary stages make the child feel alienated and hampers his/her learning. To overcome this hurdle in school education, it is suggested that the Sachar committee or its follow up Fatimi committee must have suggested provision of opening of ample number of Urdu primary schools, which is the mother tongue of large number of Muslim children in India.

- The schools need to work for bridging the gap between the school and community. This is the only way through which the drop-out rates can be reduced.

- There is an urgent need to setup schools, which are primarily oriented towards education of Muslim community. These schools should be residential in nature and quality teachers must be recruited for teaching. All the facilities for teaching have to be provided to create a conducive environment for teaching-learning.

- The disparity in Graduation Attainment Rates (GAR) is widening since 1970's and this has to be reduced as the graduates are the ultimate potential group, which can shape the future of new generation. This group becomes teachers, religious and political leaders of the community.

- Special colleges for women are to be opened, as this is a group which is generally kept away from higher education due to various cultural reasons. If kept outside then half of Muslim population is deprived of education who in turn influence remaining 50%.

- The government has to take up various strategies to bring down the gap between Muslims and other SRCs increases as the level of education increases. One such measure taken up by the government is opening of Maulana Azad National Urdu University (MANUU), which is working for reducing the gap at various levels of education. This university has opened schools, constituent colleges, university programmes in different disciplines including humanities, arts, commerce, business management, information technology, education, science, tibbiya programmes; both in distance and regular modes in Urdu medium. Such university increase both quality and quantity of education in Muslim community.
- There is poor prospectus and thereby the community is pushed towards poverty. This has to be overcome by the giving training in competitive exams at all levels in administrative services and banking sector etc. Special provisions have to be made for poverty stricken group of people.
- The poorer people are not in a position to compete for the jobs. This may be due to less exposure of educational field, lack of reservations like SC/STs, lack of availability of teachers from their community. Hence, all this leads to alien feelings and curbs learning.
- The community members must be encouraged for starting of private universities, colleges and schools within the constitutional framework.
- Government must endeavour for new plans for the community.
- Special programmes for minorities have to be launched in the form of DPEP, SSA schemes etc. This must encourage opening of new schools, recruitment of teachers, development of infrastructure and monitoring etc.
- Teacher education should be strengthened to strengthen educational base of community.
- Public and private research must be started at all levels of minorities' education from different perspectives.
- Girls' education has to be given more emphasis, as the girls of today are mothers of tomorrow. Highlighting this in one of her speech to children, the former President of India, Smt. Pratibha Patil, said "If education is given to the girls, Angels will be found everywhere". How beautiful it is to feel and experience. It is also a known fact that education of a man is education of an individual and education of a woman is education of the entire family. Hence, education of Muslim girls has to be given more emphasis.
- An inclusive policy for inclusion of Madarsa schools is to be developed. Their degrees must be given equivalence in all the universities. The share of employment may be extended to the graduates from Madarsa system.
- More dynamic strategies have to be developed for Muslim community for ensuring reservations for this community in professional courses like Engineering, Medicine and administrative services.

Conclusion

The Sachar Committee report has provided visibility to various shortfalls, shortcomings in education of minorities. It also shows that there are intra-group inequalities in education of minorities with regard to OBC, girls and those who claimed to be SC/ST among Muslims. Prof. Thorat, former Chairman, UGC and present Chairman ICSSR in one of his lectures at MANUU opined that the backwardness among Muslim is due to two factors that is general factors and discriminatory factors. Elaborating this he said poor people of upper cast in India has same problem as that of a poor Muslim. But, the opportunity to overcome their poverty reduces in case of Muslims. This shows the discrimination or exclusion factor, due to which the poorer becomes much poor. There are cases when Muslims face individual exclusion in the form of teacher or learner. At the same time they become target of social or group exclusion as in case of the exclusion of school, or college. The Sachar committee provides instances of general deprivations, where as it is the duty of scholars to take up studies on individual, group, institutional cases and make in-depth and extensive studies. The non-governmental organisations like Agha Khan Society, Azim Premji Foundation should take up these specific studies. This will help to work for the cause of education of Muslims.

Works Cited :

1. Govt. of India (2006). Social, Economic and Educational Status of the Muslim Community of India A Report. New Delhi. Author (Popularly called Sachar Committee Report)
2. Official Documentations from MANUU
3. www.censusofindia.org retrieved on January, 2013
4. <http://mhrd.gov.in/rte> retrieved on January, 2013
5. <http://www.minorityaffairs.gov.in/> retrieved on January, 2013